

THE MAIN DIRECTIONS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF STRATEGIC PLANNING AT INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES

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Annotation: *The article studies the issues of increasing the efficiency of strategic planning in industrial enterprises*

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Significant changes in the economic, social, scientific and technical conditions of the activity of industrial enterprises of our republic have changed the requirements for strategic planning in order to adapt to the external environment. The most acute struggle in world markets and the intensification of technical progress require the transformation of production, for which the acquisition of advanced equipment and technology, the results of scientific research, has become insufficient. This explains the fact that diversification has become the most common form of capital concentration.

Expanding the range and range of products or using an effective diversification strategy allows you to maintain the use of production capacities at a fairly high level and even relatively cheapen products, increase the income of enterprises and the population, better use their potential, and create a trading network. Diversification makes it possible to make better use of market opportunities, take into account its changing market conditions in terms of demand, and receive additional income by occupying profitable product niches in the market. Its advantages are manifested in the emergence in enterprises of the ability to quickly and effectively adapt to market requirements, insure themselves against risks, increase the number of sources of income, make better use of labor potential, and establish trouble-free production.

The main goal of diversification is to increase profits by using market opportunities and establishing competitive advantages, but the real ways to obtain them, and, consequently, the incentives for diversification, are different.

As you know, diversification should lead to a better use of the tangible and intangible resources of the enterprise, including through synergy. On

the one hand, it reduces the risk by eliminating the dependence of the enterprise on any one product or market, but on the other hand, it increases it, since there is a risk inherent in diversification.

The diversification strategy involves the development of new types of products at the same time as the development of new markets. At the same time, goods can be new for all enterprises operating in the target market, or only for this enterprise. Such a strategy ensures profit, its stability and sustainability in the future¹.

However, today the problem lies in the need for a rational nature of diversification, which, first of all, should identify areas that contribute to overcoming its weaknesses. To do this, it is necessary to develop an approach to the strategy of the enterprise in question, with the help of which it could adapt to unstable market conditions. At the same time, it should be taken into account that diversification should contribute to and complement the development strategy of the industrial enterprise itself.

A special role in the development of a competitive development strategy belongs to the use of modern methods and mechanisms of management and planning. At present, the reserve of competitiveness, based only on cost reduction, use of assets, logistics, is practically exhausted. Companies must find new ways to improve their operational efficiency.

The balanced scorecard was proposed by R. Kaplan, a professor at the Harvard Business School, and David Norton, president of the Balanced Scorecard Collaborative. They proved that traditional financial metrics, such as ROI and payback period, provided an incomplete and outdated picture of business performance that interfered with the creation of long-term business value, and then proposed supplementing financial metrics with data reflecting customer satisfaction, internal business processes, and the company's ability to develop and grow. This system was tested among a number of organizations participating in the project, and by the end of December 1990 the results of the work done were summed up. Based on the data obtained, the BSC was recognized as a system that allows integrating financial and non-financial performance indicators of economic activity.

The system is used as the main business management tool, which makes it possible to set individually defined goals for the employee, business units and the corporation as a whole, and most importantly, to bring them to performers at all levels of the organization². The strategy in

¹ Sirotkin S.A., Kelchevskaya N.R. Strategic planning: textbook/ Yekaterinburg: 2011. 298 p

² Abdullayeva M.N./ Matrix approach to forming a strategy for the development of industrial enterprise. Scientific electronic journal «Economics and innovative technologies» №1,2020 y. <https://iqtisodiyot.tsue.uz>. P. 150-159

this case appears to be a continuous process, in which all processes occurring in the organization receive feedback and make adjustments to the strategy. The BSC links the efficient use of tangible assets with the mobilization of intangible ones, and becomes a serious source of increasing efficiency and competitiveness. Enterprises are moving to the principle of studying the behavior, habits, preferences of existing and potential consumers in order to reflect their results in their strategy.

The company's strategy becomes an extremely important competitive instrument.

competitive struggle, and at the same time, a unique trading advantage. If we turn to the experience of leading corporations, we can see that they are moving from traditional management and control to a strategy of building consumer-oriented organizations. Tactical decisions give way to strategic ones, and the efficiency of business processes is constantly adjusted taking into account the wishes of the consumer.

Currently, the balanced scorecard is used in many leading Western companies (402 organizations from the Financial Times rating of the 500 largest companies in 2002 use this management tool³).

Using a balanced scorecard, you can evaluate business performance by linking financial and non-financial key performance indicators (for example, internal business processes, organizational development, learning and innovation). The product allows you to develop a business strategy for the entire enterprise, formalize it in the form of a BSC card, logically link it with the budgetary and organizational structure of the company, decompose strategic goals to the level of structural units and further monitor its implementation.

Thus, the issues under consideration do not claim to be indisputable. A diversification strategy is an important means of restructuring the transition economy and increasing its competitiveness. It is much more profitable to search for directions for structural adjustment by evaluating investments in sectors of the economy and business activities that have the potential for highly effective diversification of production.

The positive effect of the introduction of the BSC is due to an increase in the overall efficiency of enterprises, since with the effectiveness of the system, each of its employees is aware of the connection between their specific responsibilities and the strategic goals of the enterprise. Management, having a real mechanism to support the decision made, have the ability to measure the performance of each unit and can influence the process of implementing the chosen strategy.

³ www.novatex.ru

REFERENCE:

1. Sirotkin S.A., Kelchevskaya N.R. Strategic planning: textbook/ Yekaterinburg: 2011. 298 p.
2. www.novatex.ru
3. Abdullayeva M.N./ Matrix approach to forming a strategy for the development of industrial enterprise. Scientific electronic journal «Economics and innovative technologies» №1,2020 y. <https://iqtisodiyot.tsue.uz>. P. 150-159